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Reducing malaria transmission through reactive indoor residual spraying in response to confirmed malaria cases

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Reducing Malaria Transmission through Reactive Indoor Residual Spraying in Response to Confirmed Malaria Cases

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Background

Vector control with insecticide-treated bednets (ITNs) or indoor residual spraying (IRS) has contributed to large reductions in malaria in Africa [1]. However, vector control—particularly IRS—is expensive and as transmission declines to low levels, blanket coverage of vector control may become an inefficient use of resources. While blanket approaches become less efficient as malaria transmission declines to very low levels, case-based surveillance, namely reporting and investigating each passively-detected, parasitologically-confirmed malaria case (i.e. a symptomatic case presenting to a community health worker or a health facility), becomes more feasible.

Given the clustered nature of malaria cases at low transmission levels [2, 3], many countries pursuing malaria elimination have implemented strategies around parasitologically-confirmed malaria cases [2] in an effort to further reduce or interrupt transmission. Referred to as ‘reactive’ strategies, because they are initiated in response to confirmed cases, these actions may target both household members and neighbors of an index case, most commonly using reactive case detection (i.e. testing those around an index case for malaria and treating those positive with an antimalarial), reactive drug administration (i.e. administering an antimalarial to those around an index case without testing, regardless of symptoms), and reactive IRS of houses around an index case. Given the more focalized nature of malaria transmission in elimination settings, reactive IRS might be a more efficient approach to target transmission hotspots. China has included vector control as part of its reactive strategies, along with RACD [4], and other countries are considering shifting from blanket IRS to more targeted approaches. Despite growing interest in strategies such as reactive IRS, there has never been a systematic evaluation of the effectiveness of reactive IRS.

IRS aims to reduce malaria transmission by targeting the adult stages of the anopheline mosquito, reducing the number and longevity of adult females and thereby reducing the transmission of *Plasmodium* species, and reducing morbidity and mortality from malaria. Most IRS programs are implemented in areas of high transmission where the aim is to spray all houses and other structures in targeted areas. In these settings, IRS is conducted annually or bi-annually on a large scale (e.g. district or province) and is timed to coincide with seasonal increases in malaria transmission. In areas with lower transmission or widely dispersed populations, IRS may be done more focally, with IRS targeted to areas with higher malaria case burden as determined through health facility records and/or based on logistical considerations such as areas with higher population densities or with greater access. However, while focal IRS programs may shift targeted areas from spray round to spray round, it is generally done at the same time each year and aims for high coverage in targeted areas.

Reactive IRS differs from standard IRS programs in that it is not implemented presumptively based on pre-existing knowledge of malaria transmission but rather in response to individual cases of malaria identified. Therefore, reactive IRS is only applicable in areas that are approaching elimination where individual case-based responses are possible. Reactive IRS is done only in the house of the index case and in a pre-defined number of neighboring houses or a pre-defined area surrounding the index case. The aim of reactive IRS is to limit further spread of malaria parasites beyond the index case. Because IRS is only done in response to individual cases rather than presumptively spraying large areas, it may represent a significant cost savings compared to standard IRS.

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As countries approach malaria elimination, there is a need to adjust strategies to optimize interventions and maximize efficiency. Many countries are implementing case-based investigations along with responses that include reactive case detection, focal reactive mass drug administration and reactive IRS. These strategies offer the potential to further reduce transmission towards zero while reducing the overall cost to malaria control programs. However, there is limited data to support these strategies, particularly reactive IRS and there has never been a systematic review of evidence that does exist. This review is needed to provide support for the implementation of reactive IRS in the context of malaria elimination or to identify gaps in evidence to direct future research into the appropriateness of reactive IRS.

This systematic synthesis of available evidence and contextual considerations can inform the development of World Health Organization guidelines on the use of reactive indoor residual spraying for reducing malaria transmission in areas approaching elimination where case-based surveillance has been implemented.

Objectives

Main objectives

1. To assess the benefits (on malaria transmission or burden) and harms (adverse effects) of spraying houses of people residing with or near a parasitologically-confirmed case of malaria with a residual insecticide

Secondary objectives

1. To assess contextual factors, including values and preferences, resource use, impact on equity, feasibility, and acceptability of reactive IRS.
2. To summarize findings from mathematical modeling studies with respect to the impact of various operational factors on the modeled efficacy of reactive IRS, including size or population of the intervention area, the insecticide used, and other relevant factors

Methods

Criteria for considering studies for this review

Types of study to be included

The following types of studies were eligible for inclusion (listed in order of descending robustness):

- Randomized designs
 - o Cluster randomized controlled trials (cRCTs) with: (a) the unit of randomization being a cluster, and (b) at least two clusters per arm.
 - o Randomized cross-over trials with: (a) the unit of randomization being a cluster, and (b) at least two clusters per arm.
 - o Stepped wedge design where clusters are randomly allocated, with at least four clusters
 - o Factorial design with at least two clusters per level
- Non-randomized designs

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- o Quasi-experimental cluster-controlled trials with at least two clusters per arm
- o Controlled before-and-after designs with (a) a contemporaneous control group, and (b) at least two clusters per arm.
- o Interrupted time series (ITS) studies (with or without a contemporaneous control group) with: (a) a clearly defined point in time when the intervention occurred, and (b) at least three data points collected before the start of the intervention and (c) at least three data points after the intervention that cover the same malaria transmission season as the pre-intervention data points
- o Uncontrolled before-and-after studies (with a cluster design) or before-and-after studies with historical controls

Exclusion criteria include the following:

- Unit of randomization is at the individual level
- Unit of randomization is at the household level
- The intervention was administered to a subset of the population (i.e. based on age, occupation, etc.) in a defined geographic area
- Background malaria control interventions are not evenly distributed/balanced across study arms
- Follow-up periods for intervention and control period are not the same, or timing of baseline and endline surveys not at the same time in intervention and control
- Length of pre- and post-intervention periods for ITS studies are different (or cover different seasons)

For the secondary objectives (contextual factors and results from modeling studies), all study designs, including uncontrolled before-and-after studies, economic evaluations, qualitative studies, and other programmatic evaluations that include primary data, were considered. If there are many studies, a purposive selection of studies to cover a variety of settings would be made. If available, mathematical modeling studies, including the use of compartmental and/or individual-based models would be included to inform operational parameters and potential effect modifiers.

Types of participants

All people living in a rural or urban malarious area that is at any level of endemicity, including both stable and unstable transmission.

Types of interventions

Intervention arm

Reactive IRS entails spraying the houses of the index case and a limited number of those around the index case with a residual insecticide [5, 6]. There is no restriction on the type of insecticide used as long as it is either prequalified by WHO or is DDT. Because of the nature of the intervention, it can only be implemented and compared on a cluster level basis (e.g. village, enumeration area). The intervention must take place in a setting that offers adequate access to case management and the ability to do case-

based surveillance, i.e., conduct an investigation of each confirmed case and report cases at the individual, versus aggregate, level.

Control arm (for designs with a control group)

The control arm will include persons residing in clusters not receiving reactive IRS as described above but receiving the standard of care (including blanket IRS). Any co-interventions such as LLINs, IRS, topical repellents, spatial repellents, environmental manipulation, environmental modification, MDA, and case management must have been received in both control and intervention arms.

Background interventions

Studies where additional malaria interventions considered standard of care were implemented were included as long as interventions (both malaria and non-malaria) were balanced between intervention and control arms. Ideally, the population coverage levels of all other malaria and non-malaria co-interventions should be similar in both arms at baseline and were noted during data extraction.

Types of outcome measures

Studies must have reported at least one primary outcome or contextual factors for inclusion.

Primary outcomes

- Incidence of malaria infection: Number of cases of malaria identified through active surveillance, divided by the product of the population and the time under observation
- Prevalence of malaria infection: Number of people with malaria parasitemia (diagnostically confirmed) divided by the number tested, among a given population
- Elimination: Zero measured indigenous or local cases for a period during the peak transmission season
- Insecticide resistance: Reduced susceptibility of mosquitos to insecticide, e.g., low mosquito knock-down or mortality rates
- Incidence of clinical malaria or number of indigenous malaria cases: Number of local (indigenous) malaria cases among a certain population over a given time period; if measured by passive case detection, typically expressed as the number of cases divided by the population (for the time period specified); if measured in an incidence cohort, typically expressed as the number of cases divided by person-time
- Adverse events: Known adverse events from IRS

Contextual factors

- Values and preferences:
 - o The values and preferences of the individuals and populations affected by the recommendation with respect to the outcomes associated with the intervention
- Acceptability
 - o Extent to which those benefiting from the intervention as well as other relevant stakeholder groups consider the intervention to be appropriate (based on anticipated or experienced cognitive and emotional responses to the intervention)
 - o Willingness to participate in the intervention
- Health equity, equality and non-discrimination
 - o Extent to which the intervention:
 - Benefits all populations

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- Does not discriminate against anyone on the basis of sex, age, ethnicity, culture, language, sexual orientation or gender identity, disability status, education, socioeconomic status, residence or any other characteristic.
- Note: This could include whether the benefits and harms are equally distributed and whether the intervention is equally affordable and accessible to all
- Financial and economic considerations:
 - o Costs
 - o Resource intensiveness
 - o Overall economic impact
 - o Cost-benefit
- Feasibility and health system considerations
 - o Legal barriers to implementation
 - o Interaction with existing health system
 - o Need for and use of the existing health workforce (e.g., to conduct intervention) or other resources
 - o Programmatic considerations
 - o Note: this includes the ability to reach all targeted households/household members in a timely manner

Search methods for identification of studies

We attempted to identify all relevant trials regardless of language or publication status (published, unpublished, in press, and in progress).

Electronic database searches

We searched the following databases, using the search terms and strategy described in Appendix 2:

- Medline (OVID from 1946)
- Embase (OVID from 1988)
- Global Health (OVID from 1910)
- Cochrane Library
- CINAHL (EbscoHost)
- Scopus
- Clinicaltrials.gov
- Global Index Medicus

Reference lists

Forward and backward citation tracking was done for the reference lists of all studies and articles identified by the above methods and screened at the full text screening stage.

Conference proceedings

The following recent proceedings were reviewed for relevant abstracts: Seventh Multilateral Initiative on Malaria Pan-African Malaria Conference (Dakar, Senegal; April 2018), American Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene (ASTMH) 67th Annual Meeting (New Orleans, LA, USA; November 2018), ASTMH 68th Annual Meeting (National Harbor, MD, USA; November 2019) and ASTMH 69th Annual Meeting (Virtual; November 2020). Additionally, The Malaria Elimination Scientific Alliance assisted with conducting a 'Deep Dive' (<https://mesamalaria.org/mesa-track/deep-dives>) on each of the three intervention topics to identify planned and ongoing studies.

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Searching other resources

We contacted researchers in the field to identify unpublished data and checked the reference lists of studies identified using electronic searches.

Data collection and analysis

Selection of studies

Two review authors independently assessed the titles and abstracts of trials identified by the literature searches. At this stage, any discordance was resolved with review by a third author. We obtained the full-text articles of any potentially relevant articles. Two review authors then assessed the full-text articles of potentially relevant studies for inclusion using an eligibility form based on predetermined inclusion criteria. We resolved any disagreements by discussion and consensus, with arbitration by a third review author, when necessary. We ensured that multiple publications of the same trial were included only once. We listed studies excluded after full-text assessment, together with their reasons for exclusion, in the Characteristics of excluded studies table (Appendix 1). We illustrated the study selection process in a Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) flow chart [7].

Data extraction and management

Two review authors independently extracted information from the trials using pre-piloted electronic data extraction forms. When differences in extracted data arose, the two review authors discussed these differences to reach consensus and involved a third review author, where necessary. For missing data, we contacted the original study author(s) for clarification.

We extracted the following data.

- Trial design: type of trial; method of participant selection; adjustment for clustering (for cRCTs); sample size; method of blinding of participants and personnel.
- Participants: trial settings and population characteristics; recruitment rates; withdrawal and loss to follow-up.
- Intervention: description of intervention (active ingredient, dose, formulation, timing after index case was identified and the area/number of houses sprayed around each index case).
- Outcomes: definition of outcome; diagnostic method or surveillance method; number of events; number of participants or unit time; statistical power; unit of analysis; incomplete outcomes or missing data.
- Other:
 - primary and secondary vector(s) species;
 - phenotypic insecticide resistance (based on WHO definitions if WHO cylinder assays, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) bottle bioassays, intensity assays or synergist assays were performed while the trial was running);
 - malaria seasonality;
 - implementation of other vector and malaria control measures.

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For dichotomous outcomes, we planned to extract the number of participants experiencing each outcome and the number of participants in each treatment group. For count data outcomes, we planned to extract the number of outcomes in the treatment and control groups, the total person time at risk in each group or the rate ratio, and a measure of variance (e.g. standard error). For continuous outcomes, we planned to extract the mean and a measure of variance (e.g. standard deviation).

For cRCTs we recorded the number of clusters randomized; number of clusters analyzed; measure of effect (such as risk ratio (RR), odds ratio (OR), rate ratio, or mean difference (MD)) with confidence intervals (CI) or standard deviations; number of participants; and the intracluster correlation coefficient (ICC) value.

For non-randomized studies (NRS), we planned to extract adjusted measures of intervention effects that attempt to control for confounding.

Assessment of risk of bias in included studies

Two members of the review team independently assessed the risk of bias for each study that met eligibility criteria using a tool designed to assess such risk and generating an overall assessment as low risk, some concerns, high risk, or unclear, and summary graphs to display results. As the risk of bias in the effect of an intervention may be different for different outcomes, a 'Risk of bias' assessment for each outcome was made where appropriate. We resolved any discrepancies through discussion or by consulting a third member of the review team.

For each included RCT, the revised Cochrane 'Risk of bias' (ROB 2) tool [8] was used, along with other considerations in Chapter 8 of the Cochrane Handbook 'Assessing risk of bias in a randomized trial' [9]. Included RCTs will be rated as low risk of bias, some concerns, or high risk of bias. We planned to assess non-randomized controlled studies and ITS trials for risk of bias using Cochrane Effective Practice and Organization of Care (EPOC) 'Risk of bias' tool, and observational studies by using a version of the Cochrane Risk Of Bias In Non-randomized Studies - of Interventions (ROBINS-I) tool[10]. Non-randomized studies were to be judged overall as having low, moderate, serious, or critical risk of bias (or to have no information to judge). The ROBINS-I tool recommends only including non-randomized studies that are not classified as having critical risk of bias. Uncontrolled before-and-after studies were to be assigned a critical overall risk of bias due to the inherent biases associated with the study design. While studies with a critical risk of bias may meet the inclusion criteria, the review for such studies may include a descriptive analysis and report of their estimates of effect. Sensitivity analyses including and excluding such studies were conducted, as needed

Strategy for data synthesis

Measures of treatment effect

For study designs with a control group, the effect of the intervention was compared using risk ratios if the outcome was dichotomous, rate ratios if the outcome was a rate, counts using Poisson regression. One study was presented as the mean difference of incidence and the outcome was treated as a continuous variable. All effects are presented with their 95% CIs.

Unit of analysis issues

For cluster RCTs, measures of effect adjusted for clustering were used when possible. For studies that did not adjust for clustering, we planned to adjust the raw data using ICC values obtained from the study or authors or from similar studies or estimates of the ICC.

If studies had multiple intervention arms, treatment arms were combined as appropriate, or participants in the control group were split so that they were only included once in the meta-analysis [11].

Dealing with missing data

We attempted to contact study authors to obtain any missing data. No data imputation was applied.

Assessment of heterogeneity

For outcomes with more than one study contributing data, we planned to assess heterogeneity of main effects by examining forest plots for overlapping CIs and to examine statistical heterogeneity using the I^2 statistic. However, none of the outcomes had more than one study contributing data so inconsistency was considered 'not serious' for all outcomes.

Assessment of reporting biases

We intended to investigate reporting biases (such as publication bias) using funnel plots to assess funnel plot asymmetry both visually and using formal tests. However, this was not possible as fewer than 10 studies were identified.

Data synthesis

We analyzed data using Review Manager 5.3 (Review Manager 2014). We planned to use a fixed-effect meta-analysis to combine data if heterogeneity was absent. If there was considerable heterogeneity, we planned to combine data using a random-effects meta-analysis and reported a mean treatment effect (RRs and ORs for dichotomous outcomes and rate ratio for count data). We combined data across follow-up time points for each included study.

Certainty of the evidence

We assessed the certainty of evidence using the GRADE approach [12]. We rated each primary epidemiological outcome (malaria incidence and prevalence) as described by Balshem (2011) [13].

- High: we are very confident that the true effect lies close to that of the estimate of the effect.
- Moderate: we are moderately confident in the effect estimate. The true effect is likely to be close to the estimate of the effect.
- Low: our confidence in the effect estimate is limited. The true effect may be substantially different from the estimate of the effect.
- Very low: we have very little confidence in the effect estimate. The true effect is likely to be substantially different from the estimate of effect.

RCTs started as high-certainty evidence but we downgraded the certainty of the evidence if there were valid reasons within the following five categories: risk of bias, imprecision, inconsistency, indirectness, and publication bias. We upgraded the certainty of the evidence for studies where there was a large effect, a dose–response effect, and if all plausible residual confounding would reduce a demonstrated effect or would suggest a spurious effect if there was no effect [13]. We presented the GRADE assessments in a 'Summary of findings' tables.

Subgroup analysis

We performed sensitivity analysis on the primary outcome to determine the effect of exclusion of trials at high risk of bias (for allocation concealment and incomplete outcome data) on the overall results. If

only one study was included for a given outcome, analyses of subsets of the data by year or location were conducted.

Sensitivity analysis

We planned to perform sensitivity analysis on the primary outcome to determine the effect of exclusion of trials at high risk of bias (for allocation concealment and incomplete outcome data) on the overall results. If only one study was included for a given outcome, analyses of subsets of the data by year or location were conducted.

Results

Description of studies

Included and excluded studies are described in detail in the Characteristics of studies tables (Appendix 1).

Results of the search

We identified 457 reports using electronic searches screened all abstracts against the review's inclusion criteria. Abstract screening resulted in 20 unique reports for full-text screening (Figure 1).

Figure 1. PRISMA flow diagram

Included studies

Four separate studies met the inclusion criteria, including two studies with efficacy data and two with contextual factors. One study included both efficacy data and cost-effectiveness data. Both studies with efficacy data were cluster randomized controlled trials (cRCTs). However, one was a 2x2 superiority study where reactive IRS plus reactive case detection (RACD) and/or reactive focal mass drug administration (rfMDA) were compared alone or in combination to RACD alone [6]. The other was a non-inferiority study comparing reactive IRS to standard IRS [5].

One study was conducted from 1 January to 31 December of 2017 in the Zambezi region of northern Namibia where *Plasmodium falciparum* was the primary malaria species and *Anopheles arabiensis* was the primary vector. Annual incidence since 2010 in this region was less than 15 cases per 1000 individuals, except in the year prior to the study when incidence was 32.5 cases per 1000 individuals. However, baseline estimates in the specific study clusters for 2013-2014 was 23.5 cases per 1000 and 35.9 cases per 1000 in 2016. Routine interventions implemented by the Namibia Ministry of Health included case management, reactive case detection and annual blanket IRS with DDT. The study was conducted as a 2x2 factorial design with RACD alone, rfMDA, RACD plus reactive IRS, or rfMDA plus reactive IRS. There were 56 clusters with a total population of 18,803 individuals originally recruited into the study although one (RACD alone) was excluded as there were no incident cases during the study period. Twenty-eight clusters received reactive vector control and twenty-eight received rfMDA which was balanced across the clusters that received reactive IRS and those that did not.

The second study was conducted in Mpumalanga and Limpopo provinces of South Africa from 1 August 2015 to 31 July 2017. *Plasmodium falciparum* accounted for nearly all malaria cases and *Anopheles arabiensis* was the primary vector. Malaria incidence from 2010 to 2015 ranged from less than 1 case per 1000 person-years to 5 cases per 1000 person-years. Focal indoor residual spraying is conducted annually in these areas with pyrethroid insecticides for painted surfaces and DDT for unpainted surfaces. IRS does not cover the entire area but is prioritized to areas based on proximity to rivers and streams, malaria cases during the previous season, expert opinion of the malaria control program and the available budget. Approximately a third of houses received IRS through this method. Sixty-two clusters based on census wards were included in the study with half receiving reactive IRS and the other half receiving standard IRS. The total population in the reactive IRS clusters was 202,237 while the total population in the standard IRS clusters was 189,150.

Table 1. Summary characteristics of included studies

Study (location)	Year(s) of study	Study design	Reactive IRS		Outcomes reported (months of follow-up post-MRP)
			Insecticide (Target Dose) and Targeted Population	Number of clusters, population targeted and coverage	
Hsiang 2020 [6] (Zambezi region, Namibia)	2017	Cluster randomized controlled trial, superiority design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pirimiphos-methyl (1g/m²) • Up to 7 households within 500m of index case 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clusters = 28 • Population = 9,464* • Coverage of Index Houses = 81.6% • Coverage of targeted houses = 93.3% • Overall coverage = approximately one third 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cumulative incidence beginning 8 weeks after the first index case in each cluster • Prevalence of infection in an endline survey • Adverse events
Bath 2021 [5] (Limpopo and Mpumalanga Provinces, South Africa)	2015-2017	Cluster randomized controlled trial, non-inferiority design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deltamethrin • Up to 8 households within 200m of index case 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clusters = 31 • Population = 204,237 • Overall coverage in reactive IRS = 5% • Overall coverage in standard IRS = 30% 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mean cluster-level incidence • Adverse events (malaria deaths) • Contextual factors: financial and economic considerations

*Estimated from average cluster size of 338.

Interventions

In Namibia, reactive IRS was conducted in houses located within a 500m radius around each index case. Eligible cases were those that had resided in a study enumeration area for at least one night during the previous four weeks. Field teams visited the index case between 7 days and 5 weeks after the time of reporting. To achieve 80% coverage of eligible households, teams aimed to cover at least 7 households. Households that had been previously sprayed due to overlap with another index case were not sprayed. IRS was conducted using Actellic 300CS (pirimiphos-methyl) with a target dose of 1g/m². IRS coverage of the index case was 81.6% while coverage of targeted structures around the index case was 93.3%. Overall, it was estimated that a third of all structures in the reactive IRS arms had been sprayed.

In South Africa, reactive IRS was conducted in the index house and in eight houses within a 200m radius around each index case. Reactive IRS was conducted using pyrethroid insecticides as the primary vector (*An. arabiensis*) was considered susceptible to pyrethroids. DDT was not used as most houses in the study area had painted walls. In an endline cross-sectional survey, 30% of house structures were sprayed in the standard IRS arm compared to 5% in the reactive IRS arm.

Outcomes

Both studies measured the incidence of clinical malaria as measured through passive case detection and health facilities in the study area and both studies reported on the number of adverse events experienced. However, studies were assessed separately as the comparator arms were different.

In addition, the Namibia study measured malaria prevalence by quantitative polymerase chain reaction (qPCR) in an endline cross-sectional survey.

Contextual factors

Three studies reported contextual factors. One study was a survey of the feasibility of reactive IRS in the context of an elimination program in China where their 1-3-7 strategy aimed to report cases within one day, investigate within three days and respond within seven days. The response included reactive IRS and the aim of the study was to assess these targets were being met [14]. A second study was an adjunct to the efficacy trial conducted in Namibia. The study assessed the community acceptance of rfMDA and reactive IRS [15]. Lastly, the cRCT conducted in South Africa also included estimates of the cost-effectiveness of reactive IRS in comparison to standard IRS [5].

Excluded studies

We excluded 16 full-text articles for the following reasons.

- Protocol, abstract or cross-referenced study (8 articles)
- Background interventions not balanced across study arms (4 articles)
- Incorrect intervention (e.g. blanket IRS) (3 articles)
- No outcomes or contextual factors (2 articles)
- Not malaria (1 article)

Detailed reasons are provided in Characteristics of excluded studies (Appendix 1).

Risk of bias in included studies

Judgement of the risk of bias in the included studies was based on the revised Cochrane risk of bias tool for randomized trials (RoB2). Judgements for each included study is summarized in Figure 2 with support for judgements provided below and in the Characteristics of included studies tables.

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Bias arising from the randomization process

Both studies (Hsiang 2020 and Bath 2021) used a restricted randomization process that was clearly specified and were therefore assigned low risk.

Bias arising from the identification or recruitment of participants into clusters

In both studies (Hsiang 2020 and Bath 2021), clusters were identified before randomization. The primary outcome was incidence of malaria based on passive surveillance, so all residents of selected clusters were eligible. Although there were some differences in the baseline malaria incidence in both studies, the 95% confidence limits overlapped indicating these were not strong differences. For the Hsiang 2020 study, participants in the endline survey were randomly selected. Therefore, we considered the risk of bias arising from identification of participants to be low.

Bias due to deviations from intended intervention

No deviations from the intended intervention were reported in the Namibia study (Hsiang 2020). However, in the South Africa study, the average number of households sprayed around each index case was 3.7, well below the target of eight households per index case. The low coverage could have resulted in an underestimate of the efficacy of reactive IRS and therefore, we judged there to be a high risk of bias for this study.

Bias due to missing outcome data

Data were available from all clusters and all eligible participants in the South Africa study (Bath 2021). Data were not available from one cluster in the Namibia study (Hsiang 2020). The missing cluster was assigned to the reactive IRS arm but there were no cases in that cluster and therefore reactive IRS was not implemented. However, this was considered acceptable as no intervention could be implemented in that study cluster and this was planned for in the study protocol. Both studies were therefore judged to have a low risk of bias.

Bias in measurement of the outcome

The outcome measurement was considered appropriate and although outcome assessors were likely aware of the interventions received by study participants, malaria diagnosis was standard across arms. Therefore, the risk of bias in the measurement of the outcome was considered low for both studies.

Bias in selection of the reported result

For both studies, there were multiple analyses of the data. However, all results were reported, and the analyses included for this review were done in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan. We therefore judged the risk of bias in the selection of the reported result to be low.

Overall risk of bias

Although high risk of bias was observed in one domain in one study, the overall risk of bias was considered low for both studies.

Figure 2. Risk of bias summary: review authors' judgements about each risk of bias item for each included study

	Bias arising from randomization process	Bias arising from the identification or recruitment of participants into clusters	Bias due to deviations from intended intervention	Bias due to missing outcome data	Bias in measurement of the outcome	Bias in selection of the reported result
Bath 2021	+	+	-	+	+	+
Hsiang 2020	+	+	+	+	+	+

Effects of interventions

Incidence of clinical malaria (superiority design)

Hsiang 2020 reported a 35% reduction in the cumulative incidence of clinical malaria in clusters receiving reactive IRS compared to no reactive IRS (Risk Ratio 0.65, 95% CI 0.38-1.11, Figure 3) [6]. Analysis was done at the cluster level with cluster-level case data as the outcome and cluster-level person-time as an offset. Several models were reported adjusting for baseline malaria incidence in 2016, the response time and coverage of IRS and co-interventions. The model presented was adjusted for baseline incidence only as adjustment for baseline was specified as part of the primary analysis while the other co-variables were indicated as additional analyses [16]. The other models presented are included in Appendix 3a.

Figure 3. Forest plot of comparison: Reactive IRS vs no reactive IRS on incidence of clinical malaria, superiority design

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Footnote:

The authors calculated the effect size using marginal effects post-estimation (to account for rfMDA in half the clusters) after a regression model, thus the 95% confidence interval (CI) bounds are not balanced around the point estimate; as the Review Manager software can only accommodate balanced CIs, the 95% CI in Figure 3 contains the correct upper bound but is artificially narrow.

Incidence of clinical malaria (non-inferiority design)

Bath 2021 compared reactive IRS to standard IRS in a cRCT with a non-inferiority design [5]. Mean incidence was estimated by cluster and the mean difference between study arms was estimated as 0.10 additional cases per 1000 in the reactive IRS arm (95% CI -0.38-0.58, Figure 4). The non-inferiority bound was set at 1 case per 1000 and the analysis therefore indicated that reactive IRS was non-inferior to standard IRS. When adjusted for province, the results did not change substantially, (MD=0.14, 95%CI -0.27-0.55). Additional analyses by year and province are presented in Appendix 3b.

Figure 4. Forest plot of comparison: Reactive IRS vs standard IRS on incidence of clinical malaria, non-inferiority design

Prevalence of malaria

Hsiang 2020 reported a 68% reduction in the prevalence of malaria infection as determined by qPCR in clusters receiving reactive IRS plus reactive case detection compared to no reactive IRS (Risk Ratio 0.32, 95% CI 0.13-0.80) [6]. As for the incidence of clinical malaria, the model selected for reporting was adjusted for baseline incidence only. Other models presented by Hsiang 2020 are listed in Appendix 3c.

Figure 5. Forest plot of comparison: Reactive IRS vs no reactive IRS on the prevalence of malaria, non-superiority design

Footnote:

The authors calculated the effect size using marginal effects post-estimation (to account for rfMDA in half the clusters) after a regression model, thus the 95% confidence interval (CI) bounds are not balanced around the point estimate; as the Review Manager software can only accommodate balanced CIs, the 95% CI in Figure 3 contains the correct upper bound but is artificially narrow.

Adverse effects

Hsiang 2020 reported adverse events among persons receiving reactive IRS versus those not receiving Reactive IRS [6]. A total of 23 adverse events were reported among 18 participants. In the reactive IRS arm, 6/4579 participants (0.13%) reported at least one adverse event compared to 12/4369 participants (0.27%) in the arms that received reactive case detection alone or reactive MDA. None of the AEs were considered related to IRS.

In the study by Bath 2021 [5], comparing reactive IRS versus standard IRS over two years, 9 deaths due to malaria were reported in the reactive IRS arm out of a population of 204,237. In the standard IRS arm, a total of 12 malaria deaths were reported out of a population of 189,150.

Contextual factors

As part of malaria elimination efforts, China implemented the 1-3-7 strategy which involved reporting malaria cases within one day, investigation of cases within three days and response within seven days. The response included reactive IRS and reactive case detection for all cases determined to be indigenous and for imported cases of *Plasmodium vivax* that were in areas and seasons with ecological conditions suitable for onward transmission. Zhou 2015 assessed whether the targets for timely response were being met within the 1-3-7 framework [14]. All malaria cases were reported within the first 24 h, 98 % of case investigations were done within 3 days, and 96 % of foci investigations were done in 7 days. Among active foci, 96 % were offered treatment/RACD and IRS according to the planned schedule.

Roberts 2021 [15] assessed the acceptability of reactive focal MDA and reactive IRS within the context of the Namibia trial reported by Hsiang 2020 [6]. This mixed-methods study included key informant interviews (KIIs), focus group discussions (FGDs), and an endline cross-sectional survey while refusal rates were measured during the trial. In year 1 before the full implementation of the trial, the refusal rate for reactive IRS was high at 13.9%. Refusals were due to lack of notification before arrival, and reluctance to move furniture at short notice. In year 2, advance notification was provided and < 1% refused IRS. In KIIs and FGDs, respondents generally considered reactive IRS to be a useful tool for malaria prevention and participants in study arms that did and did not receive reactive IRS indicated a desire to have their houses sprayed. Participants specifically referenced IRS effectiveness, noting reductions in both flies and mosquitoes. In the endline survey, 624 respondents were from the reactive IRS clusters. Of these, 616 (98.7%) indicated they would participate in the same intervention again.

In addition to comparing the efficacy of reactive IRS to standard IRS, Bath 2021 estimated the cost-effectiveness of reactive IRS in comparison to standard IRS [5]. Over the two year study, the average annual economic cost was \$184,319 per 100,000 population in the standard IRS arm compared to \$88,258 per 100,000 population in the targeted IRS arm, a 52% cost savings. Using the cost per DALY, estimates of the incremental cost-effectiveness ratio were estimated overall and for each year of the study. It was estimated that overall, IRS saved \$7,845 (95% CI \$2,902-\$64,907) per additional case in the reactive IRS arm. During year 1, when incidence was low, the savings per additional DALY in the reactive IRS arm was estimated at \$35,149. The lower bound of the 95% CI was \$6,481 while at the higher bound, targeted IRS was both less expensive and more effective. In year 2, when incidence was higher, the savings per additional DALY in the reactive IRS arm was \$3,869 (95% CI \$1,371-\$50,689). The cost effectiveness thresholds were set at \$2,637 (43% of gross domestic product per capita) and \$3,557 (58% of GDP per capita). At the incidence observed in the trial, targeted IRS would have a 94-98% probability of being the cost-effective choice at either threshold. The cost effectiveness varied by year and

incidence. It was estimated that targeted IRS would remain the preferred strategy up to an incidence of 2.0-2.7 cases per 1000 person-years using the higher and lower cost-effectiveness thresholds.

Discussion

Summary of main results

Two randomized studies were included in this review: one from Namibia and the other from South Africa. Although both studies measured the incidence of clinical malaria in clusters receiving reactive IRS, the Namibia study was a superiority trial in which reactive IRS was compared to no reactive IRS while the South Africa study was a non-inferiority study comparing reactive IRS to standard IRS that has been implemented in the area for years. In addition, the Namibia study measured malaria infection prevalence by qPCR at the end of the one-year trial.

Both studies conducted reactive IRS although there were important differences in the implementation. First, the insecticide use for implementation was pirimiphos-methyl in Namibia, while in South Africa, deltamethrin was the insecticide used for IRS. However, this is unlikely to have a substantial difference as mosquito populations in both studies were reported to be susceptible to the insecticide used. Deltamethrin likely has a longer duration of efficacy than pirimiphos-methyl but given the short duration of the transmission season in Namibia, this also is unlikely to have affected the results. Another difference was in the area targeted for IRS. In Namibia, up to 7 houses were targeted in a 500m radius around index cases whereas in South Africa, 8 houses were targeted in a 200m radius around the index cases. The difference in radius likely reflects differences in population density as both studies targeted approximately the same number of households.

Based on the available data and in comparison to no reactive IRS:

- we are moderately certain that reactive IRS reduces the incidence of clinical malaria as reported by a single study (Hsiang 2020).
- We have high confidence that reactive IRS reduces the incidence of malaria infection as reported by a single study.

Based only on data and in comparison to standard IRS:

- we are moderately certain that reactive IRS is non-inferior to standard IRS in reducing the incidence of clinical malaria as reported by a single study (Bath 2021).

The frequency of adverse events was low in both studies. For the South Africa study, the only adverse events reported were malaria-related deaths which were lower in the reactive IRS arm compared to the standard IRS arm. In Namibia, a total of 23 adverse events were reported among 18 individuals. Of the 18 individuals, 6 were in the reactive IRS arm and 12 were in other treatment arms. None of the adverse events were considered related to the IRS.

While the two studies differed in design, both suggest a potential impact of reactive IRS. The Namibia study showed a significant effect on parasite prevalence in an endline survey although the impact of the incidence of clinical malaria was not statistically significant although addition models adjusting for response time and coverage and/or co-interventions suggest a significant effect of reactive IRS. In South Africa, reactive IRS was considered non-inferior to standard IRS which has been shown to be effective in reducing the transmission of malaria, particularly in areas of low, unstable transmission [17].

Overall completeness and applicability of evidence

Only two empirical studies were identified that met the inclusion criteria for this review. Both studies were conducted in southern Africa in areas where malaria transmission is low and seasonal and where it was possible to conduct case-based investigations. One study was able to quantify the cost-effectiveness of reactive IRS in comparison to standard IRS and based on sensitivity analyses, determined that reactive IRS is likely to be cost-effective in areas where the incidence of clinical malaria is no more than 2.0-2.7 cases per 1000 person-years.

Quality of the evidence

Both studies were cluster randomized trials although with different comparators. In one trial, the effect on incidence of clinical malaria was not statistically significant while the other trial was a non-inferiority study which was downgraded for indirectness. We therefore had moderate confidence that reactive IRS may reduce the incidence of clinical malaria. We have high confidence that reactive IRS will reduce the prevalence of malaria infection compared to reactive case detection one was not controlled.

Potential biases in the review process

Although we could not assess publication bias with only two studies included in the review, there is likely to have been an under-reporting of unsuccessful programmatic experiences with reactive IRS.

Agreements and disagreements with other studies or reviews

Only two studies were identified for inclusion in this study. Several other studies included indoor residual spraying as part of an outbreak response but were not included in this review as they either implemented IRS on a wider scale than reactive IRS, covering several villages or they implemented multiple malaria control interventions in addition to IRS to suppress the outbreak. It has been reported that some countries have implemented a version of IRS but published data on these efforts are lacking.

Authors' conclusions

Implications for practice

Only two empirical studies were included in this review on reactive IRS. Both empirical studies were rated as having moderate certainty for reducing the clinical incidence of malaria although one study had high certainty of reducing the prevalence of malaria. Based on a cost-effectiveness analysis, reactive IRS is likely to be cost-effective compared to standard IRS only at very low transmission settings where the incidence is no more than 2.0-2.7 cases per 1000 person-years.

Implications for research

Although the certainty of evidence was moderate to high, only two studies were included in this review. Many countries are nearing elimination and are considering the implementation of reactive strategies such as reactive IRS. Additional studies would further strengthen the evidence base for reactive IRS as well as better define the specific conditions under which it would remain cost-effective in comparison to standard IRS.

Acknowledgements

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Appendix 1: Characteristics of studies

Characteristics of included studies

Hsiang 2020

Study characteristics	
METHODS	
Study dates	1 January 2017 to 31 December 2017
Location(s) of study:	Zambezi region of northern Namibia
Baseline malaria endemicity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Malaria incidence: 23.5 cases per 1000 per year in 2013 and 2014 but an outbreak in 2016 resulted in 35.9 per 1000 per year Malaria prevalence: 2.2% prevalence by loop-mediated isothermal amplification in 2015
Peak transmission season	January to June
Malaria species	<i>P. falciparum</i>
Vector species	<i>Anopheles arabiensis</i>
Entomologic inoculation rate (EIR)	Not described
Insecticide resistance context	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 100% susceptibility to pirimiphos-methyl 98% susceptibility to DDT 71% susceptibility to deltamethrin No mutations observed in the voltage gated sodium channel
Study design	Cluster randomized controlled study, superiority design
Statistical power calculation	<p>Incidence: The study had 80% power to detect a 50% or greater relative reduction in incidence in clusters receiving either rfMDA or RAVC alone, and to detect a 75% relative reduction in incidence in clusters receiving combined interventions, with 14 clusters per study arm (harmonic mean of 276 individuals per cluster), based on an anticipated baseline annual incidence of 24.4 cases per 1000 individuals for the RACD only arm, a coefficient of variation of 0.95 based on previous incidence (in 2013 and 2014), and a two-sided significance level of 0.05.</p> <p>Prevalence: For the cross-sectional survey, 25 households in each cluster were sampled. Assuming a mean household size of four individuals and that 20% of households would not respond to the survey, a sample size of 5040 individuals provided 80% power to detect a 55% relative reduction in prevalence in individuals receiving either rfMDA or RAVC alone, and to detect an 83% relative reduction in prevalence in those receiving the combined interventions, assuming 5% prevalence of infection detected by qPCR in the RACD only arm, a coefficient of variation of 1.0, and a two-sided significance level of 0.05.</p>
Clusters or groups	<p>Unit of non-randomized group allocation: Enumeration areas</p> <p>Number of clusters selected: 56 (28 reactive IRS, 28 no reactive IRS)</p> <p>Analyzed: 55 (one cluster allocated to no reactive IRS was not included in the analysis as no index cases were observed)</p>

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	<p><u>Average cluster size</u>: 4621</p> <p><u>Design features of the clusters</u>: Enumeration areas were eligible for inclusion if they were located within the catchment area of one of the 11 study health-care facilities. Enumeration areas that had no reported incident cases or incomplete incidence data from 2012–14 were excluded</p>
PARTICIPANTS	
Population targeted	<p><u>Total</u>: 18,303</p> <p><u>Intervention</u>: 9,464 (estimated from mean cluster size of 338)</p> <p><u>Comparator</u>: 9,352 (estimated from mean cluster size of 334)</p>
Eligibility	All persons living in eligible clusters
INTERVENTION	
Insecticide and dose	Pyrimiphos-methyl, 1g/m ²
Targeted coverage around index case	80% of households within 500m of the index case with a target of at least 7 households around each index case; households that had been previously sprayed due to overlap with another index case were not eligible to be sprayed again
Actual IRS coverage	<p>Index case: 81.6%</p> <p>Targeted households around index case: 93.3%</p> <p>Overall: approximately 1/3 of households in reactive IRS clusters were sprayed</p>
Background/co-interventions	Reactive case detection and reactive focal MDA were conducted in half of the clusters. Each co-intervention was balanced between reactive IRS and no reactive IRS arms
OUTCOMES	
Incidence of clinical malaria	<u>Measurement</u> : Monthly incidence measured by microscopy at village hospitals; diagnosis by RDT or microscopy
Prevalence of malaria infection	<p><u>Measurement</u>: Cross-sectional mass blood survey at end of the study; diagnosed by qPCR</p> <p><u>Sample size</u>: 2,052 (reactive IRS); 2,030 (no reactive IRS)</p>
Adverse effects	Participants were instructed to report adverse events to the on-call study nurse or the nearest health facility.

Risk of bias

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Bias arising from the randomization process	Low risk	Allocation of treatment arms was done by a restricted randomization process
Bias arising from the identification or recruitment of participants into clusters	Low risk	All participants from selected clusters were eligible to participate in the study
Bias due to deviations from intended intervention	Low risk	No deviations from the intended intervention were reported
Bias due to missing outcome data	Low risk	Data from one cluster was dropped as no cases were identified in the cluster and therefore, no reactive strategies could be implemented. However, it was deemed acceptable to drop this

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		cluster as reactive IRS could not be implemented due to the design of the intervention.
Bias in measurement of the outcome	Low risk	The measurement outcomes (clinical malaria detected at the health facilities and prevalence of parasitemia in a cross-sectional survey) were appropriate and it is unlikely that there were differences in the measurement based on the treatment allocation.
Bias in selection of the reported result	Low risk	Although there were several possible analyses, the authors followed a pre-specified analysis plan and all possible analyses were presented.

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Bath 2021

Study characteristics	
METHODS	
Study dates	1 August 2015 to 31 July 2017
Location(s) of study:	Limpopo and Mpumalanga Provinces of South Africa
Baseline malaria endemicity	Mean annual malaria case incidence per 1000 population from 2010-2015 was 1.05 in standard IRS clusters and 0.88 in reactive IRS clusters.
Peak transmission season	January to June
Malaria species	<i>P. falciparum</i>
Vector species	<i>Anopheles arabiensis</i>
Entomologic inoculation rate (EIR)	Not described
Insecticide resistance context	Resistance to DDT or pyrethroids has not previously been observed in the study area
Study design	Cluster randomized controlled study, non-inferiority design
Statistical power calculation	Mean incidence was assumed to be 2.2 locally acquired infections per 1000 person-years. Assuming a coefficient of variation of 0.5, the trial required 31 clusters per arm with ~6000 people for 2 years (i.e. 12,000 person years per cluster) to show non-inferiority within a margin of 1 case per 1000 person-years.
Clusters or groups	<u>Unit of non-randomized group allocation:</u> Census wards <u>Number of clusters selected:</u> 62 (31 reactive IRS, 31 standard IRS) <u>Analyzed:</u> 62 <u>Average cluster size:</u> 6,588 (reactive IRS); 6,102 (standard IRS) <u>Design features of the clusters:</u> Clusters had to have a history of local cases in at least one year in the 5 years prior to the study. Where possible, clusters were separated by natural boundaries or uninhabited areas
PARTICIPANTS	
Population targeted	<u>Total:</u> 393,387 <u>Reactive IRS:</u> 204,237 <u>Standard IRS:</u> 189,150
Eligibility	All persons living in eligible clusters
INTERVENTION	
Insecticide and dose	Deltamethrin, 20mg/m ²
Targeted coverage around index case	80% of households within 500m of the index case with a target of at least 7 households around each index case; households that had been previously sprayed due to overlap with another index case were not eligible to be sprayed again
Actual IRS coverage	Targeted IRS: 5% Standard IRS: 30%

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Background/co-interventions	Reactive case detection was done in all clusters; RACD involved investigation of index cases and testing and referral of household members
OUTCOMES	
Incidence of clinical malaria	<u>Measurement:</u> Monthly incidence measured by microscopy at village hospitals; diagnosis by RDT or microscopy
Adverse effects	Malaria deaths were detected through the routine health system.

Risk of bias

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Bias arising from the randomization process	Low risk	Allocation of treatment arms was done by a restricted randomization process
Bias arising from the identification or recruitment of participants into clusters	Low risk	All participants from selected clusters were eligible to participate in the study
Bias due to deviations from intended intervention	High risk	Fewer households were targeted by reactive IRS than indicated in the original protocol. The aim was to reach at least 8 households surrounding the index case while in practice, the average number of households sprayed around each index case was 3.7
Bias due to missing outcome data	Low risk	No reports of missing data
Bias in measurement of the outcome	Low risk	The measurement outcome (clinical malaria detected at the health facilities and reported to the national malaria control program) was appropriate and it is unlikely that there were differences in the measurement based on the treatment allocation.
Bias in selection of the reported result	Low risk	Although adjusted and stratified analyses were presented, the primary outcome was presented as the crude results.

Characteristics of excluded studies

Study	Reference	Reason for exclusion
Chadee 1992	[18]	Background interventions not balanced across study arms
Chanda 2018	[19]	Background interventions not balanced across study arms
Galappaththy 2012	[20]	No outcomes or contextual factors
Galatas 2020	[21]	Incorrect intervention
Gerardin 2017	[22]	Protocol, abstract or cross-referenced study
Gueye 2018	[23]	Protocol, abstract or cross-referenced study
Hetzel 2020	[24]	No outcomes or contextual factors
Huda 2019	[25]	Not malaria
Kandeel 2016	[26]	Incorrect intervention
Karunasena 2019	[27]	Background interventions not balanced across study arms
Kleinschmidt 2017	[28]	Protocol, abstract or cross-referenced study
Larson 2015	[29]	Incorrect intervention
London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine 2015	[30]	Protocol, abstract or cross-referenced study
Medzihrandsky 2018	[16]	Protocol, abstract or cross-referenced study
Ntuku 2017	[31]	Protocol, abstract or cross-referenced study
University of California 2016	[32]	Protocol, abstract or cross-referenced study

Appendix 2. Search strategy

Database	Strategy	Records
Medline (OVID) 1946-	Malaria* AND (indoor* ADJ5 residual ADJ5 spray*) OR (in-door* ADJ5 residual ADJ5 spray*) OR pirimiphos-methyl OR vector control OR focal vector OR IRS AND Reactive OR index OR close contact*	147
Embase (OVID) 1988-	Malaria* AND (indoor* ADJ5 residual ADJ5 spray*) OR (in-door* ADJ5 residual ADJ5 spray*) OR pirimiphos-methyl OR vector control OR focal vector OR IRS AND Reactive OR index OR close contact* NOT pubmed/medline	230 -147 duplicates =83 unique items
Global Health (OVID) 1910_	Malaria* AND (indoor* ADJ5 residual ADJ5 spray*) OR (in-door* ADJ5 residual ADJ5 spray*) OR pirimiphos-methyl OR vector control OR focal vector OR IRS AND Reactive OR index OR close contact*	214 -122 duplicates = 92 unique items
Cochrane Library	Malaria*:ti,ab AND ((indoor* NEAR/5 residual NEAR/5 spray*) OR (in-door* NEAR/5 residual NEAR/5 spray*) OR pirimiphos-methyl OR "vector control" OR "focal vector" OR IRS):ti,ab AND (Reactive OR index OR "close contact*"):ti,ab.	22 -9 duplicates =13 unique items
CINAHL (EbscoHost)	Malaria* AND	20 -18 duplicates =2

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	(indoor* N5 residual N5 spray*) OR (in-door* N5 residual N5 spray*) OR pirimiphos-methyl OR "vector control" OR "focal vector" OR IRS AND Reactive OR index OR "close contact*"	unique items
Scopus	TITLE-ABS-KEY(Malaria*) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY((indoor W/5 residual W/5 spray*) OR (in-door* W/5 residual W/5 spray*) OR pirimiphos-methyl OR "vector control" OR "focal vector" OR IRS) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY(Reactive OR index OR "close contact*")	246 -177 duplicates =69 unique items
Clinicaltrials.gov	Malaria indoor residual spraying completed	12 -2 duplicates =10 unique items
Global Index Medicus	Malaria* AND "indoor residual spraying" OR "in-door residual spraying" OR pirimiphos-methyl OR "focal vector"	42 -2 duplicates =40 unique items

Appendix 3a. Additional Analyses, Incidence of Clinical Malaria, Superiority Design

Hsiang 2020 reported several models of the effect of reactive IRS versus no reactive IRS. The models followed stepwise inclusion of baseline incidence in 2016, the response time and coverage of reactive IRS and co-interventions. Three of the models did not indicate a statistically significant difference between the reactive IRS and no reactive IRS arms. Statistical significance was observed for model that included baseline incidence and co-interventions and the model that included baseline incidence, response time and coverage, and co-interventions. Because it was specified in the original analysis plan, the model adjusted for baseline incidence only was reported in Figure 2.

Figure A1. Plot of various models of the effect of reactive IRS versus no reactive IRS (Hsiang 2020)

- (1) Crude model;
- (2) Model adjusted for baseline incidence (as reported in Figure 2);
- (3) Model adjusted for baseline incidence and coverage/response time;
- (4) Model adjusted for baseline incidence and co-interventions;
- (5) Model adjusted for baseline incidence, coverage/response time and co-interventions

Appendix 3b. Additional Analyses, Incidence of Clinical Malaria, Non-Inferiority Design

Bath 2020 reported the mean difference in incidence by year and by province. In the first year, malaria incidence was low overall and the mean difference in incidence between the study arms was 0.04 cases per 1000 person-years (95% CI -0.08-0.16). The upper confidence limit did not cross the non-inferiority bound. In the second year, overall incidence of malaria was higher and the mean difference in incidence was 0.24 cases per 1000 person-years (95% CI -0.61-1.09). The 95% CI crossed the non-inferiority bound indicating that reactive IRS was non-inferior to standard IRS. However, the 90% CI did not cross the non-inferiority bound indicating that reactive IRS is non-inferior to standard IRS with 90% confidence.

Figure A2. Mean difference in incidence between reactive IRS and standard IRS by year (Bath 2020).

When analyzed by province, the mean difference in malaria incidence in Limpopo province was 0.05 cases per 1000 person-years (95% CI -1.18-1.28). The wide confidence intervals were due to the low number of clusters in Limpopo province (7 of 31 standard IRS clusters and 6 of 31 reactive IRS clusters were in Limpopo province). The mean difference in malaria incidence in Mpumalanga province was 0.17 cases per 1000 person-years (95% CI -0.26-0.60) and the upper CI did not cross the non-inferiority bound.

Figure A3. Mean difference in incidence between reactive IRS and standard IRS by province (Bath 2020).

Appendix 3c. Additional Analyses, Prevalence of Malaria, Superiority Design

As in Appendix 3a, Hsiang 2020 reported several models of the effect of reactive IRS versus no reactive IRS on parasite prevalence. The models followed stepwise inclusion of baseline incidence in 2016, the response time and coverage of reactive IRS and co-interventions. In the crude, unadjusted model, the effect of reactive IRS was not statistically significant. However, in all of the adjusted models, the prevalence of malaria was significantly lower in clusters which received reactive IRS. Because it was specified in the original analysis plan, the model adjusted for baseline incidence only was reported in Figure 4.

Figure A4. Plot of various models of the effect of reactive IRS versus no reactive IRS (Hsiang 2020)

- (1) Crude model;
- (2) Model adjusted for baseline incidence (as reported in Figure 4);
- (3) Model adjusted for baseline incidence and coverage/response time;
- (4) Model adjusted for baseline incidence and co-interventions;
- (5) Model adjusted for baseline incidence, coverage/response time and co-interventions

Appendix 4. Summary of Evidence Table

Outcomes	Anticipated Absolute Effects		Relative Effect (95% CI)	Number of Trials, Participants	Certainty of the Evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Risk with reactive IRS	Risk with standard of care				
Incidence of clinical malaria (superiority design)	30.2 cases/1000 PY (15.0-45.5)	38.9 cases/1000 PY (20.7-57.1)	RR = 0.65 (0.19-1.11)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 trial • 56 clusters (55 analyzed-28 reactive IRS, 27 no reactive IRS) • 18,303 participants (9,464 reactive IRS, 9,352 no reactive IRS) 	⊕⊕⊕ ⊖ MODERATE <i>due to imprecision</i>	
Incidence of clinical malaria (non-inferiority design)	1.05 cases/1000 PY (0.72-1.38)	0.95 cases/1000 PY (0.58-1.32)	MD = 0.10 (-0.38-0.59)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 trial • 62 clusters (32 reactive IRS, 32 standard IRS) • 393,387 participants (204,237 reactive IRS, 189,150 standard IRS) 	⊕⊕⊕ ⊖ MODERATE <i>due to indirectness</i>	Study designed as a non-inferiority trial; non-inferiority to standard IRS was demonstrated
Parasite prevalence	2.92% (2.13-3.99)	4.07% (2.92-5.64)	PR = 0.32 (0.15-0.80)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 trial • 56 clusters (55 analyzed-28 reactive IRS, 27 no reactive IRS) • 4,082 participants in endline survey (2,052 reactive IRS, 2,030 no reactive IRS) 	⊕⊕⊕ ⊖ HIGH <i>due to imprecision</i>	

PY=Person-Years, RR=Risk Ratio, MD=Mean Difference, PR=Prevalence Ratio